

An Empirical Study on “Security Analysis is a Paramount Phase in Terms of an Artificial Intelligence in 21st Century”

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:.

Khan, Barkathulla. “An Empirical Study on ‘Security Analysis Is a Paramount Phase in Terms of an Artificial Intelligence in 21st Century.’” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 80–83.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403591>

Barkathulla Khan

Associate Professor, Department of Commerce & Management
MQI Degree College, Bore Bank Road Bangalore

Abstract

In past & the present scenario Risk & Return are the two equal parallel approaches for every investor. In the competitive global world minimizing Risk & maximizing Return is the prominent challenges to every potential investors. There are several questions in front of the investors like:

- *What to Invest?*
- *How to Invest?*
- *When to Invest?*
- *From where to Invest?*

To claim all these logical & scientific reasoning investors need a feasible platform to identify an advisory support in the lights of an Artificial Intelligence (E-brokerage) who protects, council & guide 24/7 for investors Profit & wealth maximization. The main intention to present this paper is to enrich Artificial Intelligence literacy among the investors group.

Keywords: Personal finance Avenues, Performance Training Tracking Software, Stock simulation websites, Investment Portfolio Tracking websites, Performance Tracking website

Introduction

Information Technology & Communication is the modern Era in 21st century it's reduces the floor or physical trading system & gives an dynamic platform to E-Trading or paperless transactions. It's managed the time & reduces the physical brokerage & confusion among the investors. Artificial intelligence create a 24/7 financial advisory support through D-Mat process to the investors. It's an instrumental factor that support the investors transactions to make much easier like complete the quires, monitor, clear & helped spurs on its development. It plays an intermediate role for global investment avenue.

Operational software for security Analysis

Quant IX Software Investment Account Manager: This software is designed in 1985 to analyze single & multiple

portfolios. It's a centralized portfolio management for stock, bonds, mutual funds, options & Exchange traded funds etc. It's covers Asset Allocations & Diversification, Tax planning etc.

Analyze Now: This software is operate through Microsoft Excel version 97 it covers various calculations like pre & post Retirement planner, Free strategic social security planner, Returns calculators, Budgeting planner, Replacement Budgeting etc. This software is work in a tabular data format & show the results in customized chats.

Intuit's Quicken: It's Accounting software it developed in 1983. It operating system is connected to Ms-Dos, Apple II, Windows, Classic Mac OS, & IOS Android. This software covers most of the North American market requirement. It's tailored based software as per the various requirements in Account. Its covers various market place in some many countries like India, Australia, Germany, Hong Kong etc.

Social Investing Community or Sites

Trademonster.com: it’s an online brokerage site. It facilitated to investors for option trading. It’s providing information about Equities, Exchange - Trade Funds, fixed income & mutual funds. This site is executed in 15 October 2008 & it was merged into options House in 2014. It gives a place for flexible & customizable trading platform for active stock & option traders. It allows traders to access from anywhere even though mobile phones.

Covestor.com: It’s a social investing community that links client portfolio to a real brokerage account. It’s an online Investment Management site that allows the client to mirror the real trades. It’s launched in June 2007. It’s member are located in more than 100 countries & hold position in over 10000, different securities.(Ref. Wall Street journal) over 500 million US dollars in securities are shared through the service & the site has replicated 100 million US dollars worth in trades.

Morningstar.com: it’s based on investment research firm that compiles & analyses funds, stock & general market data. It also provides an extensive line of internet, software & print based products for individual investors, financial advisor & institutional clients. This site is a respected reliable source of independent investment analysis for all levels of funds & stock investors, ranging from inexperienced beginners to sophisticated experts. Morningstar filed for an Initial Public Offers (IPO) in May 2005 @ \$18.50 per share. The elected members follow an unique method of issuing public shares called Open Initial Public Offers.

SigFig: it's a new Mint - Tracking Investment website. It's a free web app analyze portfolio & delivers personalized recommendations, connecting to financial advisors. The use of SigFig is connecting the brokerage account to the service. One of the most interesting features of SigFig is it's fund & stock advices.

Conclusion

In 21st century Artificial intelligence support is a contemporary requirement for financial Management; it minimizes the geographical boundaries & maximizes Investment Avenue. Artificial intelligence shows a clear projected report card for” Time value of money “& “ Wealth maximization”.

References

- “Security analysis & portfolio management by punithavathy pandian”, *Vikas publishing House Pvt ltd*, New Delhi.
- Christopher Thornton, “Artificial intelligence strategies”, Application & Model through search second edition. Journal Wall Street
- The International Dictionary of Artificial intelligence second edition By *Global Professional Publication*.
- Wolfgang Ertel, “Introduction to Artificial intelligence”.

Web Sources

- www.Portfoliomanagement.com
- www.investopedia.com